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Fatigue Characterization Of AlSi10Mg Alloy From Variable L-PBF Processing Parameters Addressed To Hybrid Joints Of Aerostructures

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Abstract

Joining technologies in aviation are considered as a backbone. Traditional mechanical methods, like rivets and fasteners add weight, require complex assemblies, and can damage the configuration of composites such as continuous fibre breakage during handling. These challenges highlight the need for alternative solutions. The EU-funded MIMOSA project proposes a novel approach for joining metal (AlSi10Mg from Additive Manufacturing, AM) and CFRP, addressing these limitations. The proposed technology focuses on the implementation of mechanical interlocking mechanism between CFRP and 3D metal anchors based on AM (patented design and manufacturing process). The AM process associated with heat treatments requires customized fatigue characterization of the material to measure the S-N curves as function of some fundamental fabrication parameters (part orientation, surface finishing and heat treatment). This study reports the experimental results of the fatigue tests to assess the feasibility of producing the innovative multi-material joints proposed.

Introduction

This study was conducted within the framework of the MIMOSA project (Multimaterial Airframes Based on 3D Joints Between AM Metals and Carbon-Fiber Composites – GA: 101091826, Horizon 2020). The project focuses on the development of innovative hybrid joints by leveraging the design freedom of Additive Manufacturing (AM), specifically on AlSi10Mg alloy components, to improve mechanical performance and structural integration in aerostructures [1-2].

The primary goal of MIMOSA is to enhance the coupling between aluminium alloys and carbon-fibre reinforced polymers (CFRPs) by employing AM to fabricate tailored surface features - namely, interlocking anchors, with an optimized shape [3], on AlSi10Mg substrates [4]. These features are subsequently coated to improve adhesion with CFRP, creating robust metal-composite interfaces and enhancing the corrosion resistance of the joints given by the galvanic coupling [5]. This design approach has been applied to manufacture a prototype Vertical Stabilizer, demonstrating the potential for AM-enabled joints to revolutionize structural design in aviation.

The AlSi10Mg parts were produced using Powder Bed Fusion – Laser Beam (PBF-LB), a powder-based metal AM technique characterized by layer-wise laser melting of metal powders. This process offers unparalleled flexibility in part design and is particularly valuable in the aerospace sector due to its ability to reduce weight, shorten production lead times, and decentralize manufacturing operations. Key factors for achieving sustainability and supply chain resilience [6].

However, producing high-quality AlSi10Mg components via PBF-LB presents certain challenges. The rapid thermal gradients intrinsic to the process can cause defects such as porosity and cracking, which are detrimental to fatigue performance. Moreover, the high reflectivity of aluminium alloys complicates laser absorption, necessitating precise control and optimization of process parameters such as laser power, scan speed, and hatch spacing to mitigate these issues and ensure consistent mechanical properties [7].

In the context of fatigue characterization, the variability of PBF-LB parameters directly influences the microstructure, defect distribution, and surface morphology of AlSi10Mg parts [8] - all of which play a critical role in fatigue life [9].

Understanding how these parameters affect fatigue performance is essential for the reliable implementation of AM components in safety-critical aerostructures.

Euro PM2025 - Session 50: PM Aluminium Based Alloys

Beyond performance, metal AM aligns well with circular economy principles. It reduces material waste compared to conventional subtractive methods and enables the reuse of recycled materials, such as producing new metal powders from scrap through atomization. These advantages support the development of more sustainable aerospace manufacturing practices.

By investigating the fatigue behaviour of AlSi10Mg under different L-PBF process conditions, this work contributes to the optimization of hybrid metal-composite joints for aeronautical applications, paving the way for more efficient, lightweight, and resilient airframe structures.

Materials and Methods

All the specimens for the fatigue testing campaign were produced with powder bed fusion – laser beam technology (PBF-LB) using a EOS GmbH – Electro Optical Systems by F3nice srl. The material used is AlSi10Mg from EOS: the particle size distribution and the chemical composition of the powder are listed in Table 1 and Table 2.

Table 1: Particle size distribution analysis

Test method	D10 [μm]	D50 [μm]	D90 [μm]
Laser diffraction	26	47	77
Dynamic image analysis	24	40	64

Table 2: Chemistry analysis with ICP-OES method

Element	Al	Si	Fe	Mn	Mg	Ti	Zn	Sn	Cu	Ni	Pb
Limit [wt.%]	Bal.	9.0-11.0	< 0.55	< 0.45	0.20-0.45	< 0.15	< 0.10	< 0.05	< 0.05	< 0.05	< 0.05
Result [wt.%]	Bal.	9.5	0.19	< 0.01	0.32	0.01	< 0.01	< 0.01	< 0.01	0.01	< 0.01

The printing parameters used were optimized through a previous test campaign, as part of MIMOSA project [10], and are reported in Table 3. The target was to maintain the density of the printed components above 99.95%, taking into account also the small size of the pins.

Table 3: optimized printing parameters for infill and contour.

	Power [W]	Scanning speed [mm/s]	Hatch spacing [mm]	Layer thickness [mm]	VED [J/mm^3]	LED [J/mm]
Infill	352	1344	0.124	0.03	70.40	-
Contour	304	672	-	-	-	0.45

An optimization of heat treatments was also carried out; the goal was to maintain a high density and obtain good mechanical properties [10]. This analysis also took into consideration the co-curing process in the autoclave where the AlSi10Mg parts were bonded with the CFRP.

In Table 4 the optimized heat treatment HT22 is described, while Table 5 shows the tensile static properties.

Table 4: Heat treatments on specimens

Heat treatment	Stress Relieving		Solution Annealing		Quenching in water	Artificial Aging		Fast Air Cooling	Autoclave Curing	
	T [$^{\circ}\text{C}$]	t [min]	T [$^{\circ}\text{C}$]	t [min]	t [s]	T [$^{\circ}\text{C}$]	t [min]		T [$^{\circ}\text{C}$]	t [min]
HT22	200	120	530	1	30	140	360	yes	175	175

Table 5: Results from tensile tests and density measurements

Heat Treatment	Young Modulus [GPa]		Yield Stress [MPa]		Max Tensile Stress [MPa]		Max Deformation [%]		Density [%]	
	Average	Std. dev.	Average	Std. dev.	Average	Std. dev.	Average	Std. dev.	Average	Std. dev.
HT22	73	0.23	225	2.34	291	1.20	15.51	2.37	99.14	0.07

Euro PM2025 - Session 50: PM Aluminium Based Alloys

Fatigue tests were divided into three different campaigns (described in Table 6).

- Machined fatigue specimens according to ASTM E466.
 A set of 55 bulk cylindrical samples were printed with the orientation of 90° and then machined to produce the tensile specimen according to the standard with M12 threaded heads and a surface roughness of less than 0.2µm Ra. The specimens were heat treated according to the optimized HT22 (Figure 1a).
 In order to determine the Wohler diagram 15 specimens were tested at 5 load amplitude levels at a zero mean stress ($R = -1$). The other 40 specimens were tested at four different mean stresses with a staircase approach and a Haigh Diagram was determined to understand also the effect of the mean stress on the fatigue life.
- As-built fatigue specimens according to ASTM E466.
 To validate the fatigue life with the as-built roughness of the material, 30 specimens were printed net-near shape (15 specimens at 45° and 15 specimens at 90°), with the dimensions according to the standard. The specimens were heat treated according to the optimized HT22. Due to the surfaces in the final application, those specimens were also coated through Plasma spray by Johanneum Research Centre with the optimized coating selected with the double-lap pull-off tests campaign (2 layers of HDMSO + 20%CeO₂) [11]. An example is shown in Figure 1b. In order to determine the Wohler diagram the specimens were tested at 5 load amplitude levels at a zero mean stress ($R = -1$).
- Miniaturized fatigue specimens.
 30 specimens (15 specimens at 45° and 15 specimens at 90°) were printed in net-near shape, but with a miniaturized geometry to simulate the pin dimensions of the multi-material joints and also the effect of sub-surface printing defects, so the resistant section of those specimens has a diameter ca. 3 mm and their heads are threaded M6 (Figure 1c). The specimens were heat treated according to HT22 and tested with as built surface roughness after the deposition of the coating (2 layers of HDMSO + 20%CeO₂).

Figure 1. a) 15 ASTM-E466 M12 threaded machined specimens, b) an as-built specimen printed in net-near shape and coated in HDMSO and Cerium oxide with Plasma Spray and c) a miniaturized as-built specimen printed in net-near shape and coated in HDMSO and Cerium oxide with Plasma Spray.

Table 6: Test matrix for AISi10Mg fatigue campaign

Specimens type	Surface finishing	Coating	Building orientation	N. of samples	Scope
ASTM E466 threaded M12	As-Built	Plasma spray of 2 layers of HDMSO + 20%CeO ₂	45°	15	S-N curve
ASTM E466 threaded M12	As-Built	Plasma spray of 2 layers of HDMSO + 20%CeO ₂	90°	15	S-N curve
Miniaturised threaded M6	As-Built	Plasma spray of 2 layers of HDMSO + 20%CeO ₂	45°	15	S-N curve
Miniaturised threaded M6	As-Built	Plasma spray of 2 layers of HDMSO + 20%CeO ₂	90°	15	S-N curve
ASTM E466 threaded M12	Machined (Ra < 0.2 µm)	NO	90°	15	S-N curve
ASTM E466 threaded M12	Machined (Ra < 0.2 µm)	NO	90°	40	Haigh diagram

Euro PM2025 - Session 50: PM Aluminium Based Alloys

All the machined specimens were cleaned with a degreasing agent and the surface roughness was measured with a surface roughness meter. For each specimen, 5 values of roughness were taken and the mean value and standard deviation were calculated. The results were compared with the standard ASTM-E466 requirement of maximum 0.2 μm Ra of surface roughness.

Then the diameters of all specimens (as-built and machined) were measured with a caliper at three different locations along the gauge section of the specimens and likewise the surface roughness mean value and standard deviation were calculated. For the miniaturized specimens, with a large radius gauge section, only the central part was measured being the smallest and more critical for the test.

The 5 different load amplitudes for the fatigue tests were calculated according to equation 1, where the Load factor are the levels of load (5 levels) in percentage of the Yield Strength of the static tensile tests (Table 5) and the mean diameter is measured with the caliper as mentioned below.

$$\text{Load amplitude [N]} = \text{Load factor [\%]} \times \text{Yield Strength [MPa]} \times \pi \left(\frac{\text{Mean diameter [mm]}}{2} \right)^2 \quad (1)$$

Figure 2. a) Vibrant table fatigue testing machine used for ASTM specimens and b) Instron machine used for miniaturized specimens.

All the ASTM-E466 specimens with M12 threaded end sections were tested on a vibrant table, shown in Figure 2a. This testing machine is made for high cycle fatigue (10^6 cycles) and works with a threaded bar mechanism to load statically the specimen that is anchored with custom threaded adapters and two lock nuts to the machine mountings, then the alternate load is regulated adjusting the distance of a calibrated eccentric mass from its axis of rotation. The Synchronous electric motor of the vibrant table is then powered through the control panel and it rotates at a fixed speed of about 30 rpm, resulting in a frequency of the applied alternate load of about 30Hz.

The miniaturized specimens due to their small gauge section (less than 3mm in diameter) and the secondary lateral loads that are induced during the test, were too fragile to be tested on the vibrant table. For this reason, they were tested on an Instron hydraulic Universal Testing Machine (Figure 2b), using two M6 lock nuts and two rods tapped with M6 threads as adapters for centering and load transmission.

Results and Discussion

The results of measurements and fatigue tests on all the specimens are reported. In the distribution of the test results on the S-N graph (Figure 3), the interpolation lines for machined (ST1), as-built (ST0) and miniaturized (MINI) specimens printed at 90° orientation are compared on logarithmic axes. The red dotted line represents the load corresponding to the yield strength of the material as amplitude of the fatigue cycle; where the materials could reach some plastic deformation at every cycle reflecting the materials' survival limits.

The S-N curves indicate that the miniature specimens exhibit a noticeable reduction in fatigue performance at low cycles, which can be attributed to the increased defect density within the reduced gauge volume, resulting to promptly crack initiation and accelerated failure at higher alternate loads. Fatigue life is

particularly affected by surface-near defects. As a result, in smaller specimens, it is more likely that defects can be present closer to the surface having more pronounced impact on fatigue performance.

Specimens printed at a 45° orientation exhibit a slightly higher fatigue life compared to those printed at 90° (Table 7 and Table 8). This behaviour can be attributed to the alignment of the deposited layers with respect to the loading axis, which influences the crack initiation and propagation mechanisms. In the 45° building orientation, the layers are more favourably oriented relative to the applied stress, resulting in improved fatigue resistance.

Although machined specimens are generally expected to exhibit superior fatigue performance due to their improved surface finish, the resulting S-N curve appears less favourable. This discrepancy arises from the fact that the curve was generated using higher mean loads levels and consequently a higher failure rate. However, in the initial portion of the S-N curve, it can be observed that, for a given number of cycles, the failure load is higher compared to specimens in as-built condition. The improved surface finish contributes to delayed crack initiation by reducing surface irregularities and potential stress concentrators. The average roughness of the specimens results in all cases $R_a < 17\mu\text{m}$ so its influence in cross-sectional variation was assessed as negligible [12].

Figure 3. S-N curves on logarithmic axes for 90° machined, as-built and miniaturized specimens.

Figure 4. Fracture surfaces at the optical microscope of miniaturized specimens
a) MINI-04 printed at 90° b) MINI-24 printed at 45°

From the two fractographic analysis in figure 4 we could tell something more about how the fatigue crack originates and propagates at a low scale (diameters of the sections are about 3mm) and at different printing orientations. The 90° specimens show all a point of crack initiation (figure 4a) from which the main crack

Euro PM2025 - Session 50: PM Aluminium Based Alloys

propagates, but the surface defects due to net near shape printing of the miniaturized specimens start some secondary cracks that overlap with the main crack. The crack propagation seems completely different in the 45° specimens, with the presence of some V-shaped cracks starting from the surface defects, probably caused by the inclination of the printing layers respect to the fracture section.

Table 7: Loads and results of the fatigue tests on 45° HT22 as-built and miniaturized specimens.

Orientation (degrees)	As-built ASTM-E466		As- built miniaturized	
	Load amplitude (MPa)	N° of cycles	Load amplitude (MPa)	N° of cycles
45	67,5 (30%)	1000370	-	-
45	67,5 (30%)	1000370	-	-
45	67,5 (30%)	1000374	-	-
45	90,0 (40%)	1000372	90,0 (40%)	319467
45	90,0 (40%)	1000370	90,0 (40%)	1000000
45	90,0 (40%)	582791	90,0 (40%)	252841
45	101,3 (45%)	348407	101,3 (45%)	347134
45	101,3 (45%)	391663	101,3 (45%)	211463
45	101,3 (45%)	222617	101,3 (45%)	92522
45	112,5 (50%)	166081	112,5 (50%)	266912
45	112,5 (50%)	101767	112,5 (50%)	129475
45	112,5 (50%)	101342	112,5 (50%)	184339
45	123,8 (55%)	109225	123,8 (55%)	157506
45	123,8 (55%)	19151	123,8 (55%)	46037
45	123,8 (55%)	114293	123,8 (55%)	42932
45	-	-	135,0 (60%)	96236
45	-	-	135,0 (60%)	42291
45	-	-	135,0 (60%)	60219

Table 8: Loads and results of the fatigue tests on 90° HT22 as-built, miniaturized and machined specimens

Orientation (degrees)	As-built ASTM-E466		As- built miniaturized		Machined ASTM-E466		
	Load amplitude (MPa)	N° of cycles	Load amplitude (MPa)	N° of cycles	Ra mean (µm)	Load amplitude (MPa)	N° of cycles
90	67,5 (30%)	1000362	-	-	0,119 ± 0,012	67,5 (30%)	1000368
90	67,5 (30%)	1000367	-	-	0,117 ± 0,003	67,5 (30%)	245036
90	67,5 (30%)	1000371	67,5 (30%)	1000000	0,120 ± 0,016	67,5 (30%)	1000369
90	90,0 (40%)	1000357	90,0 (40%)	1000000	0,119 ± 0,018	90,0 (40%)	132781
90	90,0 (40%)	1000369	90,0 (40%)	1000000	0,108 ± 0,005	90,0 (40%)	230482
90	90,0 (40%)	356632	90,0 (40%)	232929	0,103 ± 0,012	90,0 (40%)	510776
90	101,3 (45%)	244993	101,3 (45%)	560224	-	-	-
90	101,3 (45%)	202311	101,3 (45%)	395052	-	-	-
90	101,3 (45%)	337401	101,3 (45%)	752152	-	-	-
90	112,5 (50%)	139850	112,5 (50%)	367766	0,110 ± 0,016	112,5 (50%)	147232

Euro PM2025 - Session 50: PM Aluminium Based Alloys

90	112,5 (50%)	121336	112,5 (50%)	164159	0,105 ± 0,017	112,5 (50%)	118710
90	112,5 (50%)	187142	112,5 (50%)	114821	0,104 ± 0,008	112,5 (50%)	74868
90	123,8 (55%)	106703	123,8 (55%)	113372	-	-	-
90	123,8 (55%)	94479	123,8 (55%)	169045	-	-	-
90	123,8 (55%)	84608	123,8 (55%)	97571	-	-	-
90	-	-	135,0 (60%)	104541	0,088 ± 0,007	135,0 (60%)	44444
90	-	-	135,0 (60%)	97447	0,132 ± 0,019	135,0 (60%)	66677
90	-	-	-	-	0,084 ± 0,003	135,0 (60%)	73677
90	-	-	-	-	0,125 ± 0,008	157,5 (70%)	73646
90	-	-	-	-	0,098 ± 0,013	157,5 (70%)	89032
90	-	-	-	-	0,105 ± 0,005	157,5 (70%)	55249

The Haigh diagram, shown in Figure 4, was obtained testing 40 machined specimens with building orientation of 90°. The x axis represents the mean (static) load and the y axis the amplitude of the alternate load. The purpose of this diagram is to give an area under the curve that should be considered a safe loading condition for the material with a run-out of 1 million cycles as a combination of static and dynamic loads. In red is reported the yield strength line, on which the sum of mean and alternate load is equal to the yield strength of the material and the fatigue life is really low, the blue line represents the Goodman approximation, given by the static Ultimate Tensile Strength (on the x axis) and the fatigue limit at 1 million cycles and $R = -1$ (on the y axis), obtained from the previous tests. The 40 specimens were divided in 4 batches and each tested at a different mean stress (50MPa, 100MPa, 150MPa and 185MPa) with a staircase method, starting from a value close to the Goodman approximation and then increasing the alternate load by 5MPa if the previous specimen reached runout, or lowering it by the same amount if the previous specimen failed. After the staircase testing the Dixon-Mood statistical method was applied to calculate the fatigue limit for each mean stress, obtaining the diagram.

Figure 5. Haigh diagram for ASTM-E466 90° machined specimens at 1 million cycles fatigue life.

Conclusions

The comparison of the S-N curves revealed clear trends related to surface condition and specimen size, particularly when analyzing the slope of the interpolating lines and the low-cycle fatigue regime. The effects of loading were more pronounced at higher stress levels, where differences between specimen types became more evident. A progressive decrease in the slope of the S-N curves was observed when moving from machined to as-built and miniaturized specimens, indicating a significant reduction in fatigue strength under low-cycle conditions. While the scale effect between miniaturized and as-built specimens appeared to be relatively minor, more pronounced differences were found between machined and as-built specimens. These are primarily attributed to surface finish quality and the presence of sub-surface defects inherently introduced during the near net shape additive manufacturing process. The improved surface condition of machined specimens contributed to a delay in crack initiation, leading to superior fatigue performance, especially in the early fatigue life regime. These findings highlight the critical role of surface quality and manufacturing-induced defects in determining the fatigue behavior of additively manufactured components, particularly under high loading conditions and low cycle regimes.

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Euro PM2025 - Session 50: PM Aluminium Based Alloys

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